

populations in the field are observed.

Rainfall and humidity significantly affect BPH populations. Populations are low late in the dry season. Temperature in the Mekong Delta rarely falls below 22°C or exceeds 31°C, and therefore does not limit BPH.

Natural enemies reduced BPH population in fields where no insecticide was applied. Predators such as spiders, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* and *Synharmonia octomaculata* were common. Egg parasites, mainly *Anagrus* sp., sometimes parasitized more than 90% of BPH eggs.

Rice varieties with the *bph 2* gene for resistance — IR36, IR38, IR2070, IR2071 — reduced the BPH population in the field, but IR8 and varieties with the *Bph 1* gene such as IR26, IR30, and IR1561-228-3-3 were msceptible to the local BPH population.

BPH populations have decreased since 1979 because of the intensive cultivation of IR36 and other resistant varieties.

Seasonal occurrence of BPH on rice fields in Mekong Delta, Vietnam. A = two rainfed crop areas of Long An (1978-79), and B = three irrigated crop areas of Tien Giang (1977-78).

Feeding activity of the green leafhopper (GLH) and tungro (RTV) infection

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We studied the relationship between feeding rate and number of feeding punctures by GLH and RTV infection on IR8, IR24, IR40, IR29, and IR22.

Two viruliferous GLH adults were caged in a honeydew collection chamber attached to the leaves of 20-d-old potted plants. Each variety was replicated 10 times, each chamber on a plant equaling 1 replication. The insects were allowed to feed for 22 h and the honeydew excreted by the insects was collected on filter paper treated with bromocresol green solution. The area of the honeydew spots on the paper was measured. Blue basic honeydew spots indicated phloem feeding, and were measured separately. The plants on which the hoppers fed were kept 20 d in the greenhouse for RTV symptom development and percent infection was computed.

To determine the number of feeding punctures made by GLH, 2 leaves on each

Table 1. Feeding punctures, honeydew excretion, and RTV infection, IRRI.^a

Variety	Feeding punctures (no.)	Total area (mm ²) of honeydew spots	Area (%) of basic honeydew spots	RTV infection (%)
IR8	82 c	188 b	49 b	76 b
IR24	125 a	179 b	52 b	71 b
IR40	110 ab	172 b	43 b	43 c
IR29	88 bc	179 b	10 c	14 d
IR22	45 d	228 a	100 a	99 a

^a Means in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

of 10 plants/variety were enclosed in a parafilm sachet with 2 adult GLH females. Leaf portions fed upon by the insects were cut and dipped in 1% rhodamine solution for 15 min to stain the feeding punctures pink. The punctures were counted under a binocular microscope.

Although significant differences were observed on the total honeydew excreted, percent basic honeydew, RTV infection, and feeding punctures among the varieties tested (Table 1), there was no significant correlation between total honeydew and RTV infection and between total honeydew and feeding punctures (Table 2). However, a positive

Table 2. Correlation between RTV infection and GLH feeding activity, IRRI.

Feeding activity	Correlation coefficient ^a	
	RTV infection	
Feeding punctures	0.0062	ns
Total honeydew excreted	0.47	ns
% basic honeydew	0.92	**

^a Significance at the 0.05 level = 0.666; significance at the 0.01 level (**) = 0.798. ns= not significant.

correlation between basic honeydew and RTV infection indicated that phloem feeding is necessary for RTV infection.